

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART IV

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5-Chloro-(I), 3:5-dichloro-(II), 4-methyl-5-chloro-(III) and 5-*ωωω*-tetrachloro-(IV) 2-hydroxyacetophenones have been prepared by Fries reaction. 3-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (V) and (I) have been obtained by the Friedel-Crafts reaction between acetyl chloride and *o*- and *p*-chlorophenols respectively, and subsequent hydrolysis of the acetates formed. Methyl, ethyl and propyl ethers of (I), (II), (III) and (V) have been prepared.

In extension of our previous work on this subject (this *Juornal*, 1948, 25, 277 ; 1949, 26, 243, 287) we have now synthesised a number of halogen-substituted hydroxyacetophenones and their alkyl ethers with a view to studying them for their possible insecticidal action. These compounds are expected to possess good insecticidal action as they contain in their molecule the residues of different inhalation narcotics (viz., CCl_3 , COCH_3 , COCCl_3 , OCH_3 etc.) attached to the poisonous chlorobenzene ring ; that this type of combination is essential for a good contact insecticide is already known (Busvine, *Nature*, 1935, 156, 169). Five hydroxyketones, viz., 5-chloro-(I), 3:5-dichloro- (II), 4-methyl-5-chloro- (III), 5-*ωωωω*-tetrachloro-(IV) and 3-chloro- (V) 2-hydroxy-acetophenones have been prepared ; (I), (II), (III) and (V) have been subsequently converted into their methyl, ethyl and propyl ethers. It may be mentioned that a number of alkyl halogen phenols have already been shown to possess good bactericidal properties (Klarmann, Shternov and Gates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2576).

(I), (II), (III) and (V) have been prepared by the Fries rearrangement of the corresponding acetates. The first three of these compounds have been previously obtained by this method by several authors (Wittig, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 88, 1270 ; *Annalen*, 1926, 446, 155; Karrer *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1930, 13, 1308 ; Klarmann *et al.*, *loc. cit.* Chien and Yin, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 7, 40 ; Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56). *o*-Chlorophenyl acetate could not be rearranged even on heating at 140° for 8 hours with 1½ mole of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

The Friedel-Crafts reaction between acetyl chloride and *p*- and *o*- chlorophenols in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride resulted in a formation of the acetates of 5-chloro- and 3-chloro-2-hydroxy-acetophenones respectively in very good yields (cf. Nencki and Stoeber, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1771 ; Claus, *Chem. Zentr.* 1898, II, 158; these authors have carried out the above reaction in presence of anhydrous ferric chloride, and obtained 5-chloro-2-hydroxy- and 3-chloro-4-hydroxy- acetophenones in the case of *p*- and *o*- chlorophenols respectively). These acetates yielded the corresponding phenols on hydrolysis with alkali.

The methyl, ethyl and propyl ethers of (I), (II), (III) and (V) were obtained in good yields (60-90%) by using dimethyl sulphate, ethyl iodide and propyl bromide respectively. Methyl ethers of 2-hydroxy-5-chloro- and 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro- acetophenones have been previously described, the former having been obtained by the action of acetyl chloride on

The salt separates in white micro-crystalline state. In composition, it resembles the corresponding salt of bismuth, unlike which, however, it is readily soluble in water with gradual decomposition with separation of S. [Found : K, 19.58 ; La, 23.32 ; S, 32.71. $K_3La(S_2O_3)_3$ requires K, 19.76 ; La, 23.48 ; S, 32.43 per cent].

6. *Potassium Cerium Thiosulphate*.—The method of preparation is the same as above substituting cerous acetate in place of lanthanum acetate. It resembles the lanthanum salt in all respects. [Found : K, 19.57 ; Ce, 23.65 ; S, 32.60. $K_3Ce(S_2O_3)_3$ requires K, 19.73 ; Ce, 23.61 ; S 32.37 per cent].

7. *Potassium Praseodymium Thiosulphate*.—The salt was prepared in the same way as the other salts from praseodymium acetate and potassium thiosulphate. The salt separates in light green micro-crystals, readily soluble in water with decomposition. [Found : K, 19.57 ; Pr, 23.72 ; S 32.45. $K_3Pr(S_2O_3)_3$ requires K, 19.69 ; Pr, 23.73, S, 32.32 per cent].

8. *Potassium Neodymium Thiosulphate*.—The method of preparation is the same as above which it resembles in all respects. The salt is obtained in light rose colour. [Found : K, 19.65 ; Nd, 24.06 ; S, 32.31. $K_3Nd(S_2O_3)_3$ requires K, 19.59 ; Nd, 24.16 ; S, 32.14 per cent].

9. *Ammonium Lanthanum Thiosulphate*.—For the preparation of the ammonium salts the rare earth iodides are used. The salt is obtained from lanthanum iodide and ammonium thiosulphate in the same way as other alkali salts.

The ammonium salts, also, have the composition similar to the corresponding bismuth salts. It is readily soluble in water and the aqueous solution decomposes gradually with separation of sulphur. [Found : NH_4 , 10.12 ; La, 26.15 ; S, 36.36. $(NH_4)_3La(S_2O_3)_3$ requires NH_4 , 10.21 ; La, 26.28 ; S 36.29 per cent].

10. *Ammonium cerium thiosulphate* was prepared in same way as above. [Found : NH_4 , 10.16 ; Ce, 26.38 ; S, 36.14. $(NH_4)_3Ce(S_2O_3)_3$ requires NH_4 , 10.19 ; Ce, 26.47 ; S, 36.23 per cent].

11. *Ammonium Praseodymium Thiosulphate*.—The method of preparation is the same as above. The salt separates in green micro-crystalline precipitate [Found : NH_4 , 10.12 ; Pr, 26.48 ; S, 36.24. $(NH_4)_3Pr(S_2O_3)_3$ requires NH_4 , 10.17 ; Pr, 26.55 ; S, 36.16 per cent].

12. *Ammonium neodymium thiosulphate* was obtained as above as light rose crystals. It readily dissolves in water with gradual decomposition with separation of sulphur. [Found : NH_4 , 10.21 ; Nd, 27.12 ; S, 36.15. $(NH_4)_3Nd(S_2O_3)_3$ requires NH_4 , 10.11 ; Nd, 27.02 ; S, 35.96 per cent].

Methods of Analysis

The compound was first decomposed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and filtered. The rare earths were precipitated from this filtrate twice with ammonia, the hydroxides

dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitated with oxalic acid as oxalates and the oxalates were then ignited to oxides. The filtrates from ammonia precipitation were mixed together, evaporated to dryness, ammonium salts removed by ignition, residue treated with a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid, excess removed and alkalis weighed as sulphate. Sulphur was estimated in a separate sample as BaSO_4 after oxidation with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide and separation of rare earth hydroxides. Ammonium in ammonium salts were estimated by Kjeldahl's method after distillation with caustic soda, absorbing the evolved ammonia in standard acid and titrating the excess acid back with standard alkali.

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